

CONSTRUCTING THE CONTOURS OF INDIA'S FOREIGN POLICY TOWARDS CHINA IN WEST ASIA

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Abstract:

Since their Independence, the foreign policy of India and China have largely been determined by their domestic goals and national commitments. But, over the last decade India has moved from being non-aligned to being multi-aligned and China from being neutral to non-interventionist. The aim, the popular discourse reports, is at global leadership and in filling the vacuum in the balance of power vis-a-vis a weakening western hegemony; and by virtue of being co-regionals and neighbours, the dimension of competition therefore enlarges. Apart from their neighbourhood, West Asia is a strategic region where this competition is projected to grow. However, this paper argues that India and China are not in a state of competition, and that India should not succumb to this needless projection. In making its argument the researcher uses the Rationalist theory of International Politics.

While both India and China voice the concerns of the Global South, and advocate for an Alternate World Order, their strategic variables to international discourse and their global outlook varies. India has held a more cooperative approach with the West, as against China's confrontational approach. While China's rise in the region is in conformity with the West Asian Powers attempts to diversify or fundamentally a relation building against which they can bargain with the United States, India's growing partnership in the region is based on mutual commitment to growth and development for a post-oil economy. There is no denying that India is gradually but significantly seeing a strategic role in the region especially with the I2U2 grouping and the India - Middle East - Europe Corridor, but these are not necessarily a competitive challenge to China's growing footprints. India is undertaking its individual growth journey encompassing

different sectors of space, technology and food security, while also focusing on building its security capabilities and partnerships.

This paper takes a step ahead in suggesting that not only is there no competition between India and China, but that the co-operation between these two powers in West Asia is mutually beneficial.

Keyword: India, China, Foreign Policy, West Asia, Competition, Co-operation

1. Introduction

Transition from National Commitment to Global Impact

John F Kennedy had once said, “The purpose of foreign policy is not to provide an outlet for our own sentiments of hope or indignation; it is to shape real events in a real world” (Iqbal, 2024)

And that is the understanding of Foreign Policy that this paper is based on. Since their Independence, the foreign policy of both India and China have largely been determined by their domestic goals and national commitments. But, over the last decade India has moved from being non-aligned to being multi-aligned and China from being neutral to non-interventionist (Basu, 2024) (Mechanix, 2022). The aim, the popular discourse reports, is at global leadership and in filling the vacuum in the balance of power vis-a-vis a weakening western hegemony; and by virtue of being co-regionals and neighbours, the dimension of competition therefore enlarges (Xavier, Baruah, & Madan, 2023).

Apart from their neighbourhood, West Asia is a geopolitically strategic region where this competition is projected to grow. However, this paper deals with the question, if India and China really have conflicting interests in West Asia? and should India engage in this projection? Going forward, this paper also deals with the scope of cooperation over competition between these two powers in West Asia. In making its argument the researcher uses the Rationalist theory of International Politics.

2. Research Gap

Identifying the gap in existing research

There is a great deal of literature and study on India-China relations: bilaterally, in the neighborhood, and more recently in the larger global domain. However, major studies have been through the Balance of

Power theory of Realism, Securitization theory, Game theory or with a Constructivist approach.

Research Gap: There is lack of comparative study on the different variables that determine India and China's Foreign Policy in analyzing the prospects of their relations in West Asia.

3. Theoretical Framework

The Approach of study

The paper uses the Rationalist theory of International Politics proposed by Charles Glaser which is rooted in the idea that 'anarchy does not have a single logic, leading to competition', but that under certain circumstances 'cooperation can be states' best option' (Zufle, n.d.). The theory focuses on three variables that define a rational state's strategy: state's motives (interests and goals), material variables (like military capacity) and information variables (information about adversary's motives and the information the state believes the adversary has of its own motives) (Glaser, 2010).

Figure 1: Prepared by the Researcher

Using these three variables this paper presents a comparative study of India and China's motives in West Asia, their capacity building, and their outlook towards each other in the region, using descriptive and analytical methods.

4. Factorizing the India-China Relations

A Comprehensive Perspective

From Panchasheel to 1962 war to newer efforts in Mamllapuram to the Dokhlam standoff, India-China relations have been complex (Chauhan,

2020). While there is strain and stagnancy in the bilateral relations, they continue to co-operate in the multilateral forums like BRICS, SCO, G20 and others (Kirton, & Larionova, 2022).

In the Global Landscape in general and in West Asia in particular the India-China relations cannot be seen in isolation, there are other factors that influence:

- Challenges that they face in the immediate neighborhood
- America's de-prioritization of West Asia
- West Asia looking for diversification
- Rise of the Global South, and its assertion for multipolarity
- Abraham Accords and the new alliances like Iran-China-Russia Nexus
- The ongoing war between Israel and Hamas makes the situation further complex.

[The future of the normalization agreement which was fast materializing has now become uncertain (This despite the fact that India and UAE helped Israel overcome the Houthi's challenge in the Red Sea by transporting goods through Jordan into Israel). Further, President Erdogan and President Al-Sisi met after years of fractured ties to discuss the war in Gaza, and President Bashar al Asad is regaining acceptability in the region. This in a way signifies failure of America's policy in the region.]

5. India's Foreign Policy Objectives in West Asia

National Progress and Collective Growth

India has had historical and civilizational ties with the region (E.g. Mesopotamian civilization, Persian Civilization). However, since independence the four major driving force of India's West Asia policy has been Energy resources, Remittances from the diaspora, the Palestinian cause and the also determined by the South Asian Politics that is to counter Pakistan's influence in the region especially on the issue of Kashmir (Anas, 2021). But over the last decade or so India's outlook and objectives in the region has expanded to a more strategic

engagement especially under the “Look West Policy” (Kotecha, & Khatik, 2018). There are growing economic activities with the region in terms of trade and investments in the field of energy security, food security, defense, technology, manufacturing, transportation, space, health, education and sustainability (Joshi, 2023).

The significance of the region in India’s foreign policy can be understood from the following data:

- Around 8.9 million Indians reside the Gulf and nearly 50% of India’s over \$ 80 billion remittances comes from here (Rahman, 2023).
- Nearly 60% oil and gas imports are from gulf.
- UAE is India’s 3rd largest global trading partner (2024). And, with the signing of the Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement in 2022 the trade has increased by over 38% to \$ 88 Billion (“CEPA is the Growth Engine for India-UAE Bilateral Trade, n.d.).
- Saudi Arabia is India’s 4th largest trading partner and is heavily investing in India’s infrastructure, manufacturing, digital and renewable energy sectors (Consulate General of India, Jeddah,” n.d.).
- While India’s relations with most countries in West Asia has been evolutionary, it has seen a revolutionary growth in its relations with Israel at least in the last decade. Israel is among the top 3 suppliers of defense equipments to India, and nearly 43% of Israel’s arms exports are being sold to India (Reuters, 2024).
- India also has good relations with the non-gulf countries like Egypt, Turkey and Iran.

In 2023 India and Egypt signed the strategic partnership agreement committing to cooperation in defense and security, in economic, scientific and academic collaborations and in promoting cultural and people to people contact. Also, Egypt President was Chief Guest at Republic Day function last year (ANI, 2023). The bilateral trade between the two countries is recorded at \$7.26 billion in 2022, and is expected to rise to \$12 billion in next five years (2022).

As India aims to be a leading voice of the Global South, and given the geopolitical significance of West Asia, its constructive engagement with the region beyond the bilateral trade is crucial for India's global ambitions.

In this regard India's relation with West Asia can be understood under the following heads:

Indo-Abrahamic Alliance

Earlier India was in a paradoxical situation with regards to its relations and engagement with the Arab countries and Israel because of the absence of diplomatic relations between these countries over the Palestinian issue. But with the Abraham Accords and the normalization of relations, it has given a push to the India's wholistic engagement with the region. What is also important here is the desire of the West Asian powers to diversify their economy and strategic associations in order to establish a balance of power and give way to multipolarity ("The Abraham Accords, Explained," 2023), in which they, especially Mohammad bin Salman sees India as a credible and stable partner as they can pursue areas of common interest such as technology, energy, maritime security and trade.

I2U2 grouping

Established in 2021 and popularly called the Middle East Quad, the I2U2 is a very strategic grouping with America – a super power, Israel – an intelligence and technology center, UAE – the biggest business center of the world and India – the fastest growing economy. Geopolitically, it is expected to balance the rise of not just China but also Iran and Turkey (Mayer, Afterman, & Janardhan, 2023). For India the grouping bolsters economic ties and deeper engagements with West Asia. In fact, under this grouping there has been a rise of a \$ 7 billion Middle East Food Security corridor, through which India hopes to become the food basket of West Asia, receiving capital from UAE and technology from Israel. UAE has already invested \$2 billion in the construction of food parks in India (Soliman, 2023).

India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor

Established on the sideline of the G20 summit in India, the corridor aims to give enhanced connectivity and economic integration to boost

economic development in the region through rail, road and sea routes. It is seen as an alternate to the Belt and Road Initiative of China (“IMEC and BRI: Beyond Complementary Competition,” n.d.).

India-Israel Relations

With the present government in center, India and Israel have found ideological cohesion. They see each other as great friends, and have increased cooperation in intelligence sharing, technology transfer, arms deal, and counter terrorism initiatives – which is seen by policy analyst as the ‘New Middle East Strategy’. PM Modi immediately came out in support of Israel post the October 7th Hamas attack on Israel (Ganguly & Blarel, 2023). However, days later Foreign Office had to put out a statement advocating for a two-state solution and protection of Human Rights and adherence to International Law following Israel’s counter offensive in Gaza (Paliwal, 2022).

India will have to carefully stride through its relation with Israel given the fact that a major part of Global South does not support Israel’s agenda in Palestine. It is also important to note that beyond trade and technology, India is also important for Israel to enhance and expand its credibility and normalization. Israel’s former National Security Advisor, Maj Gen Yaakov Amidror, told PTI, “India can also help to enhance and expand the scope of the Abraham Accords by bringing in new countries” (S, & Kumar, 2023). India should be careful in serving Israel’s agenda on its own credibility. It was widely reported that India had sent military drones to Israel in the midst of the ongoing war, and had also helped Israel bypass the threat to Houthis in the Red Sea through UAE and Jordan (Mathews, 2024).

India-Iran Relations

Because of the sanctions, and India’s growing bonhomie with US and Israel, the relations with Iran have remained strained and stagnant. This has also stalled India’s ambitious Chabahar project (Gurjar, 2023). Since 2018 there has been steep fall in the bilateral trade. However, with the Saudi-Iran deal, the rise of Taliban in Afghanistan, and the ever-present China and Pakistan factor India is under geo-political compulsions to re-energize its ties with Iran.

US factor in India's West Asia discourse

United States is India's largest trading partner and both countries share a strategic relationship (2023). As US looks to downsize its role in West Asia it views India's increased role in the region to fill the vacuum in order to prevent China from assuming that role. America already recognizes India as a major player in West Asia. And this is critical challenge for India's independent policy in the region.

India's Soft Power Diplomacy

Besides trade, cultural relations are a key aspect of India-West Asia relations which India seeks to foster through the strength of its diaspora. The inauguration of the grand temple in UAE by the PM Modi in his 7th visit to the nation is a recent example, and so is the release of the navy veterans from Qatar a result of its growing soft power in the region (PTI, 2024). In fact, India sent in large scale aid to Turkey and Syria after the Earth Quake last year as it wished to be seen as the country of first response providing disaster relief and humanitarian assistance. Also, the recent visit by Minister Smriti Irani became the first non-Muslim delegation to the holy city of Madina, displaying the close cord between the two nations (Wajihuddin, 2024).

6. China's Engagement in West Asia

The Sleeping Dragon Awakes

Once described as a sleeping dragon, China has now emerged as a formidable power threatening to drag the existing powers in the Thucydides trap (according to which an emerging power threatens to displace an existing great power). Earlier, as a growing economy, like in the case of India, China's primary engagement with the West Asian region was with an intent to secure stable energy supply. But over the last decade its domain of engagement and sphere of influence has quietly but strategically enlarged encompassing economic, geopolitical and strategic considerations ("China Regional Snapshot: Middle East and North Africa – Committee on Foreign Affairs," 2022). In fact, in 2022 China held two crucial summits in the region – China Arab States Summit and China-GCC Summit (Eslami & Papageorgiou, 2023).

There could be primarily three reasons for it:

1. Its economic interests (in terms of access to vital resources and markets), and making its infrastructural expansion viable
2. China's assertive stands in geo-politics shows that it now wishes to be seen as a World Power
3. To counter balance United States growing influence in the Indo-Pacific – South China Sea, Taiwan and Hongkong issues – makes it compelling for China to move out of its own region and challenge the United States in its region of primary influence so as to both divert attention, and also maintain a balance of power

One critical aspect of Chinese expansion in the region is its non-interventionist approach which is appealing to the West Asian Powers which are seeking more autonomy in their foreign policy decisions while looking for diversification (Sahide, 2023).

There are three major domains through which China's West Asia engagement can be understood:

1. Economy and Infrastructure
2. Military and Technology
3. Diplomacy

Economy and Infrastructure

China is now GCC's largest trading partner, Saudi and UAE's largest non-oil trading partner, and UAE's second largest trading partner. It is also actively looking to establish Free Trade Agreement with GCC members.

- a. Chinese companies have heavily invested in ports and energy infrastructure especially along the Strait of Hormoz (from where 1/3rd of the seaborne crude oil transits).

Figure 2: Dire Straits; Source: Centre for Strategic and International Studies

Now, in doing this they are following their successful experience, and a text book case, in Djibouti across Bab-al-Mandab where they first established their infrastructure for civilian purpose and then expanded it to support the military. This is what the Chinese scholars label as “first civilian and then military.” The three critical ports where China is heavily investing is – Khalifa port and Fujairah port in UAE, and Duqm port in Oman. A subsidiary of the China’s shipping giant COSCO inked a \$738 million agreement to construct a container terminal at Khalifa. China Petroleum Engineering and Construction Company invested \$ 3.3 billion to construct Habshan – Fujairah Oil Pipeline to bypass Hormuz. Another, state owned company Sinopec holds 50% stake in a major terminal at Fujairah. Further, consortium of Chinese companies has signed a 50-year lease with Duqm Special Economic Zone Authority to

co-develop China-Oman Industrial Park (Funairole, Hart, & McElwee, 2023).

- b. China is also expanding its Belt and Road initiative in the region. According to China BRI Investment Report 2021, the majority of the Chinese BRI investment projects in 2021 targeted this region (Lons, Fulton, Sun, & Al-Tamimi, 2019).

Figure 3: China's BRI; Source: European Council on Foreign Relations

China has invested \$ 10.5 billion in construction contracts in Iraq making it the top recipient of China's BRI financing for infrastructure projects in 2021 (Wang, 2022). It is to further invest another \$10 billion in infrastructure projects in the Autonomous Kurdistan Region in North Iraq. But the most interesting of all is the Iran-China "Comprehensive Strategic Partnership" agreement, which is estimated to be \$400 billion, corresponding to 10% of China's total BRI budget (Nouri, & Parmar, 2023). A significant part of this agreement, is the joint development of the Chabahar port, and a new oil terminal near the Jask port, south of the Strait of Hormuz. Several Chinese companies are also involved in constructing the UAE's national Etihad rail network, which will connect several ports with major trade and industrial hubs throughout the Arabian Peninsula (Bhatia, 2020).

Military and Technology

China has increased its arms sale in West Asia including the sale of advanced weapons like Dongfeng ballistic missiles and Wing Loong

Bomber drones, a kind which the U. S has for long denied to the region (Ateed, 2023). China has also conducted military exercises with both Saudi Arabia and Iran, and has signed a joint venture for weapons production with Saudi Arabia (Taneja, 2023).

China Navy has a significant presence in the region and has supported Chinese anti-piracy escort missions in the Gulf of Aden since 2008. In 2021 U. S intelligence agencies have accused China of secretly constructing military facility at the Khalifa port. Nonetheless, it is an established fact that, China's Department of Defense has listed UAE among the countries where the PLA has considered establishing an overseas military facility. Even without having a formal military base the sensors placed into Chinese-owned port terminals can assist in collecting intelligence signals on other militaries (Brar, 2024).

Further, Beijing is also extending its digital footprints in the region to expand its role as a high-tech power and use data as a tool to promote economic transformation and development. Under this ambition Chinese companies have secured 5G deals with the GCC countries. In fact, UAE has selected Huawei as its 5G partner (which created friction with the U.S and led to freezing the sale of F 35 stealth fighters, in response to which UAE suspended \$23 billion arms deal with United States). Also, Saudi Arabia is now supporting Chinese investments in advanced technology and research. China has also boosted its cooperation with Israel in technology and infrastructure (Gill, 2021).

Diplomacy

As stated above, China has vested interest in maintaining peace and stability in the region. It has played key role in peace promotion and mediation efforts in Syria, Yemen and Afghanistan. But its biggest achievement has been the Iran-Saudi Agreement in 2023 (Jazeera, 2023). This is a diplomatic victory also because, for long United States has been accused to fostering the “divide and conquer” approach in the region between the Arab Countries and Iran. China altered this status quo which Iran has described as a ‘strategic peace’ against US hegemony (Godement, 2023). Further, Saudi-Arabia, Iran and Qatar are now also members of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization. Moreover, the kind of reception that Chinese premier received in the BRICS summit at South Africa in 2023, shows China's growing global influence and its initiative and support to include Egypt, Iran, Saudi Arabia and UAE into

the BRICS fold shows its prospering diplomatic clout (Aluf, 2024) (Harding, 2023).

China has also advanced its soft power projection in the region by providing aid during the pandemic, cultural promotion, people to people contact and university exchange programs. These have helped it present a positive image in the region and highlight its role as a responsible power.

7. India-China Relations in West Asia: A Rationalist Analysis

Past Chapters, Present Trajectories, and exploring a New Course

- a. Though West Asia is significant for both India and China, their outlook of the region and nature of **interest variable** vary. While India approaches the region with soft power initiatives, China's soft power engagement in the region has a harder undertone. This is also evident in how the region views both India and China. While it sees India as a partner for future goals of sustainable growth and development, it views China as an alternate in its geopolitical diversification project. Since the nature of our relation with the region varies, we are not in a state of direct conflict or competition with China, and therefore shouldn't engage in such a projection.

However, there is a tricky situation for India – though both India and China are emerging global leaders and aspiring voices of the global south, the nature of their engagement with the prevailing dominant geopolitical forces especially the United States. While India adopts a more cooperative approach in its multipolarity stand, China has a confrontational approach. And, this in certain cases allows leverage to China (Jacob, 2024). For example:

1. The kind of influence that China exercised in the BRICS Summit in South Africa to include new emerging economies of the global south in its fold.
2. At a time when we were expecting US to broker a deal between Saudi Arabia and Israel, China brokered between Saudi Arabia and Iran (Joshi, 2023).

Therefore, if India wishes to be seen as a leader of the global south it will have to be careful of the extend of its relations with the West and their allies. For example:

1. Prime Minister Modi came out with an unequivocal support for Israel after the October 7th attacks. The Foreign Ministry did issue statements reiterating India's support for the Two-State Solution, but that was only couple of days later. China, on the other hand despite having good trade relations with Israel, did come out in an unambiguous support for Palestine (Caliskan, 2023).

At a time when major part of the global south is with Palestine, India was seen supplying military drones to Israel, and helping it escape the Houthi challenge in Red Sea (Khalil, 2024).

2. We downplayed our relations with Iran under the influence of sanctions. Despite the fact that Iran is important to us in many ways: energy resources, strategic location at the Strait of Hormuz, being a gateway to Central Asia, with the rise of Taliban in Afghanistan, being a major center of the North-South transport corridor, and our major stakes in Chabahar.

Iran also becomes important for India because of two new grouping: Tehran-Beijing-Moscow Axis, and the Turkey-Iran-Pakistan-Malaysia Bloc.

One would recall that after the outbreak of the Russia-Ukraine War both Saudi Arabia and UAE refused to take calls from President Biden over regulating oil production, and just months later gave a purple carpet welcome to President Xi (Helmore, 2022). This in many ways was a churn in the existing global order, and a symbolic rise of the alternate.

However, the fine balance that India needs in its relations with the West is for its own credibility in the Global South, and not as a challenge to China. Truth be told, China is in a state of rising cold war against the United State particularly in West Asia, and not with India. For India to be a World Power, its stands on Global Affairs have to be assertive and principle based.

- b. In terms of **material variable** whether military or infrastructural capacity and building, China is in an unmatched position. However, in West Asia this is not an immediate threat for India. In fact, if China's presence in the region is able to ensure balance of power

and therefore stability, and the two can cooperate in ensuring security of maritime trade, then it is in India's interest. And, for the long-term India is building its security capacity. Also, the view that the new IMEC is to challenge the BRI, is misplaced. Is anyone ready to argue that countries in West Asia are going to abandon BRI for IMEC. Definitely not. Of course, this route will create new avenues and ensure greater connectivity favorable to India's business and its engagement with West Asia and beyond.

- c. The other critical area of understanding India-China relations, is the **information variable**, that is: what we know and understand of China's global outlook and ambition and what they do of us. It is the deficit in the information variable that leads to suspicion, which could be one of the major reasons for the recent border standoff. And, to deal with this it is important that there be sustained and intense interaction and exchange programs at all levels of government, academia, and people to people contact. It is not that only India needs a relation of cooperation with China, China also cannot afford a strained relations with India given its already prevailing challenges in its South and South East. One would recall that Chinese delegation led by its foreign minister was one of the first to come to India, after the Russian Ukraine war.

8. Discussion and Policy Recommendation

Critical Assessment of a multi-layered engagement

- a. One of the major aims of India's Foreign Policy has been democratization of the World Order and enhanced multipolarity. And, in the great power influence, the weaker the hegemon the greater is the possibility for new powers to rise. And, in the particular case here, with China and India, a multipolar West Asia will reduce the risk of destabilizing regime change operations.

Observation: India is United States partner in interest, and not in values. And, partnerships based on interests are always vulnerable. Further, United States history of partnership beyond its traditional western hemisphere has not been very good. In fact, Henry Kissinger has himself said about the United States that, "To be an enemy of America is dangerous, to be its friend is fatal." Also, United States will never confront China directly, therefore,

associating with the United States in its provocative measures against China will bear repercussions solely for India.

Therefore, to suggest that India's non-alignment is a policy of the past is misplaced. Non-alignment or its enhanced version of multi-alignment lies at the crux of India's foreign policy, and will continue to remain crucial given India's geopolitical positioning.

- b. To be a World Power India needs an assertive and principled foreign policy (Horimoto, 2017).
- c. India needs to reorient its neighborhood engagement. Nepal has accused India of big brother attitude, Bhutan is inching close to a boarder deal with China, the military junta in Myanmar has China's backing and is negotiating a peace talk with the rebel group, Sri Lanka is caught in the Chinese debt trap, over the years our relations with Maldives as also deteriorated and they have accused us of big power dominance (Freeman, 2017). And, this neighborhood crisis doesn't necessarily have to do with China's String of Pearls policy, but India's own shortcomings in its foreign policy ("India-China Competition: Perspectives from the Neighbourhood," n.d.).
- d. Taking that forward, this paper suggests that normalizing ties with Pakistan and revitalizing the SAARC grouping is in the larger interest of India, especially in the changed geopolitical scenario. With the rise of Taliban in Afghanistan, the growing nexus among Tehran-Beijing-Moscow, and though stagnant the Turkey-Iran-Pakistan-Malaysia bloc, it is important that India look forward to reorienting its relations with Pakistan and revitalizing its relations with Iran.
- e. West Asia is a huge market, and as members of the global south India and China have more areas of cooperation than competition in realizing the aim of achieving an Asian Century.

9. Conclusion

The Merit in Collaboration

In his address to the Heads of Indian Missions in February 2015, Prime Minister Narendra Modi had said, 'India needs to position itself in a leading role, rather than just a balancing force'

In the light of this outlook is the main submission of the paper that, India as a rising power and a fast-growing economy with a huge stable market is geopolitically in a sweet spot. It should capitalize on its own potentials and foster its engagement and relations globally based on its own national agendas and its commitment to collective growth. As an emerging power to encourage the projection of being a challenge to yet another rising power is not in the interest of India's ambitions of being a World Power. India and China have more to gain in collaboration, than competition.

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